

Complex Metal-ammonium Selenites and Selenito-metalammines.

BY PRIYADARANJAN RÂY AND AMALENDRA NARAYAN GHOSH.

Although cobalt complexes containing the sulphito-, sulphato- (Riesefeld, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, **132**, 99), chromato- (Briggs, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **115**, 67) and selenato- (Mayer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, **118**, 1) groups have been known for some time, very few attempts have been made to prepare the corresponding selenito-compounds. Only recently Riley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2988) has described the preparation of two pentammine selenito-complexes of cobalt. No other stable complex selenite of cobalt or any other metal has been reported, though Hahn, Seigert and Meir (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, **150**, 126) have isolated a series of double selenites.

As the important series of sulphito-ammine complexes has been so thoroughly investigated, it seemed desirable to study complexes containing the analogous selenito-group. The preparation and properties of some of these compounds have been described in this paper.

As has been pointed out by Riley (*loc. cit.*), the selenito-radical, like the corresponding sulphito-group, occupies only one co-ordination position inside the complex zone. But contrary to the behaviour of the sulphito-ion, the selenito-ion appears to have very little tendency to enter the complex zone, being readily displaced from the co-ordination sphere by water (hydrolysis). This lack in the power of forming stable complexes may be ascribed to the increased heaviness of the ion and the decreased electronegative character of selenium. Unlike the sulphito-complexes, the selenito-complexes are highly soluble and extremely hygroscopic, their isolation in the solid state in a pure form being rather difficult.

The salts of the series are ruby-red in colour and, by inference from comparison with sulphito-complexes, the selenito-group may be considered to be linked to the central atom through oxygen (*cf.* Werner, *Annalen*, 1911, **386**, 81; Duff, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 452).

Further, as no ammino- or substituted ammino-complexes of copper and nickel selenites have been reported, the preparation and properties of a few of these complex selenites have been described in this communication.

The nickel selenite gives both tetra- and hexa-co-ordinated amines, whereas copper-ammine selenites are only tetra-co-ordinated, suggesting an influence of the nature of the anion upon the co-ordination capacity of the central metallic atom.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Triethylenediamine Cobaltic Bicarbonato-selenite

Cobalt selenite, $\text{CoSeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5 g.), prepared by precipitation from a solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by Na_2SeO_3 , was shaken with 40 c. c. of a 10% solution of ethylenediamine hydrate. The mixture was oxidised by vigorous current of air for 12 hours. The selenite gradually dissolved and the solution became yellow as the oxidation proceeded. After the oxidation was complete, the filtered solution was concentrated on the water-bath and treated with absolute alcohol. The yellowish brown precipitate was filtered, dissolved in water, and the aqueous solution saturated with CO_2 . The solution was again concentrated on the water-bath and again precipitated by alcohol. The yellow crystals were dried to a constant weight in vacuum over H_2SO_4 .

The substance forms highly soluble, brownish yellow crystals, which effervesce with dilute acids. Barium chloride gives with the cold and neutral solution a complete precipitation of barium carbonate and barium selenite showing that the HCO_3' and SeO_3'' are outside the complex zone. (Found: N, 18.95; Co, 12.64; CO_2 , 9.85; Se, 17.02. Theory requires N, 18.93; Co, 12.76; CO_2 , 9.52; Se, 17.06 per cent).

Triethylenediamine Cobaltic Selenite, $[\text{Co (En)}_3]_2 (\text{SeO}_3)_3, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Triethylenediamine cobaltic bicarbonato-selenite, prepared, as described above, was treated with half the molecular proportion of selenious acid dissolved in water. Brisk evolution of CO_2 occurred. The solution was concentrated on the water-bath and the crystals precipitated by absolute alcohol. These were redissolved in water and reprecipitated with alcohol. They were then filtered, washed with absolute alcohol, and dried to a constant weight in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . (Found: N, 17.96; Co, 12.45; Se, 25.50. Theory requires N, 18.04; Co, 12.60; Se, 25.50 per cent).

The substance forms highly soluble golden yellow crystals. Barium chloride added in excess to a neutral solution causes an immediate and complete precipitation of barium selenite, showing that all the selenium is present as anion.

Diaquo-diethylenediamine Cobaltic Chloroselenite.

Carbonato-diethylenediamine cobaltic chloride, $[\text{Co En}_2 (\text{CO}_3)] \text{Cl}$ (10 g.) was treated with a solution of selenious acid (5 g.) in the cold, when a rapid evolution of CO_2 occurred. The solution was warmed on the water-bath and was treated, after concentration, with absolute alcohol at 0° . The salt separated as an oil which gradually solidified on repeated washing with alcohol by decantation. The substance was dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 .

It forms highly soluble red-violet hygroscopic crystals. Silver nitrate produces a white precipitate in cold aqueous solution. A part of the precipitate dissolves in nitric acid and the insoluble part in ammonia. This proves that both Cl' and SeO_3'' are outside the complex zone. (Found : Cl, 9.0, 9.11 ; Co, 15.64, 15.63 ; Se, 20.03, 20.35. Theory requires Cl, 9.16 ; Co, 15.28 ; Se, 20.45 per cent.).

Monoquo-diethylenediamine Selenito-cobaltic Chloride.

Cobalt selenite (10 g.), 10% ethylenediamine solution (52 c. c.) and ammonium chloride (2 g.) were mixed and oxidised by a current of air in the cold. The red cobalt selenite gradually dissolved; the air current was continued for some hours after the cobalt selenite had all dissolved. The red solution was concentrated in vacuum over H_2SO_4 and treated with alcohol. Some reddish brown crystals separated; these on analysis, were found to be triethylenediamine cobaltic chloride, $[\text{Co En}_3] \text{Cl}_3$, and were filtered off. The mother liquor was again concentrated in vacuum and treated with alcohol. This precipitated an oily liquid which was washed thoroughly with alcohol by decantation and then evaporated to dryness in vacuum over H_2SO_4 .

The substance forms highly soluble ruby-red hygroscopic crystals. Cold aqueous solution gives no precipitate with ammoniacal barium chloride solution, but, on boiling, a white precipitate of barium sele-

nite appears. This shows that the selenito-group is present inside the complex. If a very cold solution is treated with an excess of silver nitrate, rapidly filtered and the filtrate boiled, a white precipitate of silver selenite soluble in acid is obtained. But all the selenium is precipitated in the cold if the solution is kept in contact with silver nitrate for any length of time. A gradual hydrolysis of the selenito-complex leading to the formation of a diaquo-compound occurs. (Found: N, 13.78, 13.78; Cl, 8.94, 8.82; Co, 14.51, 14.52; Se, 19.07, 19.35. Theory requires N, 13.79; Cl, 8.87; Co, 14.52; Se, 19.50 per cent).

Cryoscopic measurements.

G. of salt in 100 c.c. soln. calc. on the anhydr. basis.	Depression of F.P. = Δ .	M.W. from $\Delta = m$.	Vant Hoff's factor $i = M/m$.	Degree of dissociation $\alpha = \frac{i-1}{(n-1)}$
3.2784	0.340	173.57	2.07	1.07
1.1835	0.130	163.87	2.20	1.20
0.59175	0.070	152.15	2.37	1.37

where M denotes the mol. wt. calculated and n , the number of ions into which the substance should dissociate.

The value of α indicates that the salt is considerably hydrolysed in aqueous solution. The determination of equivalent conductivity also points to the same conclusion.

Conductivity measurements at 25°

λ , for	v (litres) \rightarrow						
	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
[CoEn ₂ (H ₂ O)SeO ₃]Cl	91.2	103.6	115.6	121.4	139.3	150.6	157.7
[CoEn ₂ (SO ₃)]Br	—	89.32	99.24	108.1	115.1	122.8	127.6
[CoEn ₂ (S ₂ O ₃)]Br	—	83.18	90.65	96.90	104.1	113.0	118.5
[CoEn ₂ (SO ₄)]Br	—	90.4	98.5	106.9	114.0	119.7	125.2

The conductivity values of the last three compounds are those given by Duff (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 454).

Aquodiethylenediamine Selenito-cobaltic Nitrate.

Cobalt selenite (10 g.), 10% ethylenediamine solution (52 c.c.), and

ammonium nitrate (2.5 g.) were mixed and oxidised, when almost all the selenite dissolved; the solution was filtered and further oxidised for two hours. The deep red solution was concentrated on the water-bath and then left in the ice-chest for a few hours. The cooled solution was afterwards treated with alcohol; and the oily liquid, that separated, was washed with alcohol by decantation. This was dried to a constant weight in vacuum over H_2SO_4 .

The substance forms red hygroscopic powder resembling the chloride in properties. It is much more easily hydrolysed than the chloride. Silver nitrate completely precipitates all selenium even in the cold. Ammoniacal solution of barium chloride does not precipitate barium selenite in the cold. The precipitate appears only on heating the solution. (Found : N, 17.72 ; Co, 14.07 ; Se, 18.80. Theory requires N, 17.65 ; Co, 13.98 ; Se, 18.75 per cent).

Aquo-diethylenediamine Selenito-cobaltic Bromide.

Cobalt selenite (5 g.), 26 c.c. of ethylenediamine solution (10%) and 1.4 g. of ammonium bromide were mixed and oxidised by a vigorous current of air. The selenite gradually dissolved; the solution was filtered, and the filtrate further oxidised for some hours. The solution was then concentrated on the water-bath and cooled. Yellow crystals of $[Co En_3] Br_3$ separated out and were filtered off. The filtrate was left in the ice-chest for some hours. The cooled solution was treated with small amount of alcohol to free it from any triethylenediamine compound. When the latter salt separated no more, the selenitobromide was precipitated from the solution as an oil by an excess of alcohol, and washed free from impurities.

It forms deep red extremely hygroscopic powder, shows properties resembling those of the chloride, and is more easily hydrolysed. Barium chloride and excess of ammonia brings about a slow precipitation of barium selenite. (Found : N, 13.83 ; Br, 19.70 ; Co, 13.91 ; Se, 19.62. Theory requires N, 13.86 ; Br, 19.80 ; Co, 14.06 ; Se, 19.60 per cent).

Aquo-diethylenediamine Selenito-cobaltic Sulphate.

Cobalt selenite (5 g.), 10% ethylenediamine solution (26 c.c.) and 1 g. of ammonium sulphate were mixed and oxidised as in the above described preparation. The concentrated solution was cooled for 3 hours and was freed from any triethylenediamine salt by repeated

treatment with small quantities of alcohol. The solution was then treated with excess of alcohol, when an oily liquid separated, which was washed several times by decantation with alcohol. This was dried to a crystalline powder in vacuum over H_2SO_4 .

The substance forms red hygroscopic powder, highly soluble in water. Its properties are similar to those of the other salts. Treated with an excess of ammoniacal barium chloride, the aqueous solution gives an immediate precipitation of barium sulphate (insoluble in acids), and the filtrate gives a precipitate of barium selenite (soluble in acids) on boiling. This shows that SeO_3 is present inside the complex and SO_4 exists as an anion. (Found: N, 4.70; Co, 14.92; Se, 20.36; SO_4 , 12.33. Theory requires, N, 14.38; Co, 14.94; Se, 20.36; SO_4 , 12.30 per cent).

Triethylenediamine Nickel Selenite, $[\text{Ni En}_3] \text{SeO}_3$.

Nickel selenite, $\text{NiSeO}_3 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5 g.) was treated with 47 c.c. of a 10% ethylenediamine hydrate solution and then digested on the water-bath. The selenite dissolved and the solution turned violet-red; the filtered solution was evaporated on the water-bath with constant stirring. Pale red, extremely deliquescent crystals were thus obtained. These were dried at 100° to a constant weight.

Barium chloride gives a complete precipitation of barium selenite from its aqueous solution. Acids decompose it readily. Nickel is completely precipitated from an ammoniacal solution of the salt by dimethylglyoxime. (Found: N, 23.16; Ni, 16.25; Se, 21.25. Theory requires N, 23.0; Ni, 16.05; Se, 21.64 per cent).

Diethylenediamine Nickel Selenite, $[\text{Ni En}_2] \text{SeO}_3 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Excess of nickel selenite was digested with ethylenediamine solution. After filtering off the undissolved selenite, the blue solution was concentrated in vacuum over lime. A blue hygroscopic crystalline solid was obtained.

The blue powder is highly soluble in water; the solution on warming decomposes with formation of triethylenediamine salt depositing nickel selenite. Digestion with ethylenediamine hydrate leads also to the formation of the triethylenediamine compound. (Found: N, 16.23; Ni, 17.52; Se, 23.85. Theory requires N, 16.60; Ni, 17.58; Se, 24.0 per cent).

Hexammine Nickel Selenite, $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6] \text{SeO}_3$.

Hydrated nickel selenite was suspended in alcohol and treated with a current of dry ammonia. The selenite gradually dissolved, the solution becoming blue and then violet. From the violet solution, pale violet crystals were precipitated by the continuous passage of ammonia. The unstable violet substance was quickly filtered in a cold funnel, dried in the folds of a filter-paper and introduced into a dried and weighed vessel. This was then dried thoroughly by passing a current of dry ammonia for several hours till the weight became constant.

The substance readily decomposes on exposure to air, first turning blue and then green with complete loss of ammonia. The solid can be kept unchanged in an atmosphere of ammonia at a temperature below 52° —its decomposition point. (Found : NH_3 , 35.51; Ni, 19.45; Se, 27.50. Theory requires NH_3 , 35.49; Ni, 20.12; Se, 27.50 per cent).

Diethylenediamine Copper Selenite, $[\text{Cu En}_2] \text{SeO}_3$.

A solution of copper sulphate (5 g.) was treated with calculated amount of sodium selenite. The precipitated copper selenite was washed and treated with ethylenediamine solution. The blue solution thus obtained, was evaporated to dryness in vacuum over sulphuric acid to a constant weight.

The substance forms blue hygroscopic crystals having a beautiful violet reflex. It readily dissolves in water forming a deep blue solution and remains unchanged by treatment with ethylenediamine hydrate. It is decomposed on heating in air, and also by acids. Barium chloride solution causes an immediate precipitation of barium selenite in the cold. (Found : N, 18.05; Cu, 20.37; Se, 25.04. Theory requires N, 18.02; Cu, 20.43; Se, 25.49 per cent).

Tetrammine Copper Selenite, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4] \text{SeO}_3$.

Precipitated copper selenite was treated with dry ammonia. On absorption of ammonia the mass became hot and the colour changed to deep blue. The mass was thoroughly dried by continuous passage of ammonia for some hours till the weight became constant.

The substance forms deep blue hygroscopic crystals decomposing on exposure to air. It dissolves in water forming a blue solution, which

readily decomposes by losing ammonia. (Found : Cu, 24.45 ; NH₃, 26.28 ; Se, 30.98. Theory requires Cu 24.61 ; NH₃, 26.28 ; Se, 30.60 per cent).

SUMMARY.

1. The preparation and properties of a number of complex metal-ammonium selenites and selenito-metalammines with Co⁺⁺⁺, Cu⁺⁺, and Ni⁺⁺ as the central atoms and containing ammonia and ethylenediamine have been described.

2. Only in the case of some cobaltic complexes the selenito-group has been found to enter the complex zone, while it exists as an anion in all other cases. The co-ordination bond holding the selenito-group is very weak and is easily ruptured by water (hydrolysis). This might be attributed to the increased heaviness of SeO₃^{''} and the decreased electronegative character of selenium. Like the sulphito-group, the bivalent selenito group occupies only one co-ordination position.

3. Both tetra- and hexa-co-ordinated nickel-ammine selenites have been obtained, whereas copper-ammine selenites are only tetra-co-ordinated. This suggests an influence of the nature of the anion upon the co-ordinating capacity of the central metallic atom.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
CALCUTTA.

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